

How Trust Helps in Improving Firm Performance via Supplier Network Responsiveness and Competitive Advantage- An Empirical Study

Ambreen Shakir

Research scholar

Department of Business Administration, AMU, Aligarh, India.
ambreenshakir04@gmail.com

Dr. Salma Ahmed

Professor

Department of Business Administration, AMU, Aligarh, India.
salmaahmed6@rediffmail.com

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Trust is important in every relationship, whether personal or professional. When we discuss the relationship between a manufacturer and its supplier, trust also exists. This study was conducted on the relationship of a manufacturer with its supplier to know the presence and “effect of trust” on firm performance via supplier network responsiveness and competitive advantage. Keeping in mind the importance of trust in supply chains, this study conceptualises the role of trust by suggesting a model and hypotheses for improving supply chain responsiveness, which in turn results in competitive advantage and improved firm performance. The existing literature on trust proves why trust is important in different organisational relationships, but a specific study on the role of trust in a manufacturer-supplier relationship has not been conducted. In addition, no study shows a direct relationship between “trust”, “SC responsiveness”, “competitive advantage”, and “firm performance”.

Keywords: Trust, supplier network responsiveness, competitive advantage, firm performance, supply chain.

1. Introduction

A concept called “keiretsu”, introduced by Japanese manufacturers, has become very popular nowadays in the business world. The concept Keiretsu denotes “harmony and cooperation” among the members of a supply chain and places emphasis on building a long-term and strong relationship with each other (Monczka et. al. 2002, Ouchi W 1980, Prescutti W. 1992). As a result of this system, Japanese firms observed a significant reduction in cycle time. After that, Japanese firms started working with their suppliers which resulted in giving benefitted both parties. Japanese manufacturing firms always take care of their suppliers by providing support, such as investments in equipment and other specific assets, as per the requirement of a particular supplier (Nishiguchi, 1994). As a result of vertical keiretsu, Japanese manufacturing firms have gained a competitive advantage over their competitors (Dyer 1996).

In today’s competitive world, manufacturing firms are forced to operate in an environment full of demanding customers (Rich & Hines, 1997). In this era of competition, product life cycles and time to market have become short, and customers are demanding good quality products and services at low cost with a faster response (Yang and Burns, 2003; D’ Souza, 2000). For today’s manufacturing firms, responsiveness is considered one of the important factors to win more orders from their prospective buyers (Narasimhan and Das, 1999). That is why supply chain management should be done in such a way that it yields a spontaneous reaction to the changing demands of buyers (Sabath, 1998).

There are many sources of competitive advantage, including supply chain responsiveness (SC) is one of them (Lau & Hurley, 2001). Supply chain responsiveness (SC) helps companies lower uncertainties and adapt to demand fluctuations (Randall et al., 2003). Thatte (2007) stated a positive significant impact of “supply chain responsiveness” on “competitive advantage”. Yusuf et. al (2004) established a positive effect of “supply chain responsiveness” on “time to market, dependability, product innovation and quality”. A responsive supply chain is basically a reduction in lead time which further helps in reducing time to market (Towill 2002). Supplier network responsiveness helps a firm to compete with its rival firms on “product innovation”, “time to market”, and providing product delivery on time. A firm can achieve a competitive advantage through price, quality, and dependable delivery if it has a quick and responsive “supply chain” (Li et al., 2006). “Supply chain responsiveness” of a firm depends upon all the processes of its “supply chain” i.e., suppliers, operations, and logistics. On the basis of these three processes/functions of a supply chain SC responsiveness can be divided into three types- “operating system responsiveness”, “logistics process responsiveness”, and “supplier network responsiveness” (Thatte 2007). For the purpose of this study, only supplier network responsiveness is considered, as the researcher is interested in considering the relationship between the manufacturer and its supplier.

2. Literature Review

Author	Year	Conclusion
Lau and Hurley	2001	“There are many sources of getting competitive advantage, supply chain responsiveness (SC) is one of them”.
Handfield and Bechtel	2002	“Trust is essential in improving supply chain relations which in turn helps in improving supply chain responsiveness”.
Kwon and Suh	2004	“Presence of trust helps in improving relations between supply chain members which in turn makes the supply chain more responsive towards the dangers present in the environment”.
Yusuf et. al.	2004	“There is a positive relationship between supply chain responsiveness and time to market, dependability, product innovation and quality”.
Cater and Pucko	2005	“Firms who have competitive advantage, whether cost advantage or product differentiation advantage or both, are more successful than those who have no competitive advantage”.

Li et al.,	2006	“A firm can achieve competitive advantage through price, quality, and dependable delivery if it has a quick and responsive supply chain”.
A. Thatte	2007	“There is a positive relationship between supply chain responsiveness and competitive advantage”.
Sinkovics et. al	2011	“Trust in a supply chain relationship helps in achieving better cooperation among the supply chain partners which in turn helps in achieving more supplier responsiveness”.
Li Liu	2011	“Competitive advantage has a noticeable impact on firm performance”.
Stonehouse and Snowdon,	2014	“Competitive advantage improves firm performance by giving desired value to the customers and desired profits to the firm”.
Santanu Mandal	2015	“Critical information is also shared if there is trust in a business relationship which further help the supply chain partners in making the supply chain more responsive”.

2.1 “Trust” to “Supplier Network Responsiveness (SNR)”-

According to Svensson (2004), “trust is an important factor in business relationships since people manage the business activities.” Morgan and Hunt (1994) opined that trust is “a firm’s belief in its partner’s trustworthiness and integrity”. “Supply chain responsiveness” can be defined as “the ability to change quickly in terms of volume, mix or location as a function of changing conditions” (Melnyk et al., 2012). It is generally measured in terms of the reduction in cycle time (Handfield et.al. 1998, Handfield R, Nichols E. 2002). Handfield and Bechtel (2002), reduction in cycle time within supply chain is one of the major indications of good and healthy inter-organisational relationship. For a quick response to the evolving environment, firms also need to change their competitive priorities. Owing to rapid changes in competition, firms are forced to adopt cycle-time-based strategies to cope with changing conditions. According to Handfield and Nicholas (2002), “suppliers who are able to respond quickly to changes in order volumes through strategies such as vendor managed inventory, just in- time delivery, and inventory positioning within the supply chain can significantly improve customer satisfaction.”

“Supply chain responsiveness” includes “operations system responsiveness”, “logistics process responsiveness”, and “supplier network responsiveness”. When we discuss the relationship between a manufacturer and its supplier, supply chain responsiveness means supplier network responsiveness. It is essential for a firm to have trust in its partner firm or supplier for the smooth operation of its business. According to Handfield and Bechtel (2002), trust is essential in improving “supply chain relations” which in turn helps in improving supply chain responsiveness. Kwon and Suh (2004) also said that presence of trust helps in improving relations between supply chain members as a result supply chain becomes more responsive towards the dangers present in the environment. Critical information is also shared if there is trust in a business relationship which further helps supply chain partners make the supply chain more responsive (Santanu Mandal, 2015). According to Sinkovics et al. (2011), trust in a supply chain relationship helps achieve better cooperation among supply chain partners which in turn helps achieve more supplier responsiveness.

H1: A higher level of trust in the supply chain has a significant impact on supplier network responsiveness.

2.2 “Supplier network responsiveness” to “Competitive Advantage”

In order to succeed in today’s business world full of competition, “supply chains” should be fast, flexible, and ready to respond according to the needs and demands of the global marketplace (Thatte et. al, 2013). There are many sources of competitive advantage, including supply chain responsiveness (SC) is one of them (Lau & Hurley, 2001). Supply chain responsiveness (SC) helps companies lower uncertainties and adapt to demand fluctuations (Randall et al., 2003). Thatte (2007) stated a positive impact of “supply chain responsiveness” on “competitive advantage”. Yusuf et. al (2004) established “a positive

relationship between supply chain responsiveness and time to market, dependability, product innovation, and quality”. A responsive supply chain is basically a reduction in lead time which further helps in reducing time to market (Towill 2002). Supplier network responsiveness enables a firm to compete with its rival firms on “product innovation”, “time to market”, and providing on-time delivery. A firm can achieve a competitive advantage through price, quality, and dependable delivery if it has a quick and responsive “supply chain” (Li et al., 2006). “Supply chain responsiveness” of a firm depends upon all the processes of its “supply chain” i.e., suppliers, operations, and logistics. Based on these three processes/functions of a supply chain, SC responsiveness can be categorised as “operating system responsiveness”, “logistics process responsiveness”, and “supplier network responsiveness” (Thatte 2007). For the purpose of this study, we have only taken supplier network responsiveness into account, as we are interested in considering the relationship between the manufacturer and a supplier.

H2: A higher level of supplier network responsiveness has a significant impact on competitive advantage.

2.3 “Competitive Advantage” to “Firm Performance”

A firm is said to achieve “competitive advantage” over its competitors when it is able to deliver same products to its customers at a cost lower than its competitors i.e., cost advantage or is able to give more benefits to its customers as compared to its competitors i.e., product differentiation advantage (Bambang Leo Handokoa, Rudy Aryantob, Idris Gautama So, 2015).

“Competitive advantage” possesses a direct and positive relationship with “firm performance”. According to Li Liu (2011), “competitive advantage” has a noticeable impact on “firm performance”. “Competitive advantage” improves “firm performance” by giving desired value to the customers and desired profits to the firm (Stonehouse and Snowdon, 2014). Firms that have a competitive advantage, whether cost advantage, product differentiation advantage, or both, are more successful than those that have no competitive advantage (Cater and Pucko, 2005).

H3: Competitive advantage has a significant impact on firm performance.

2.4 Theoretical Framework

This empirical study is based on the gaps present in the existing literature. A model and hypotheses were proposed to test the relationship between the manufacturer and supplier. In this model, the independent variable is “trust in the supply chain,” and the dependent variables are “supplier network responsiveness”, “competitive advantage”, and “firm performance”. Out of the relationships of all the members of a supply chain, we take only the relationship between the manufacturer and supplier in this study. That is why we are assessing only supplier network responsiveness here. Competitive advantage will be measured in terms of “cost, quality, delivery dependability, time to market, and product innovation”. The proposed framework is an

adaptation of the three different models proposed by Handfield and Betchel (2002). Thatte 2013, and Handoko et. al. 2015.

Fig: 1 Theoretical Framework Model

2.5 Objectives

1. To examine the impact of presence trust on supplier network responsiveness.
2. To examine the impact of a responsive supply chain on a firm’s competitive advantage
3. To examine the impact of gaining a competitive advantage on firm performance.

3.1 Research Design

This is a single descriptive cross-sectional study designed to examine the presence and effect of trust on firm performance via supplier network responsiveness and competitive advantage. The study established the cause-and-effect relationship between the constructs, and the data were collected from the target population only once by drawing a single sample of respondents.

3.2 Sampling and Data Collection

The population of the present study was supply chain managers working in Indian automobile companies manufacturing passenger cars and the Indian electronics industry. Middle- and senior-level professionals working in the supply chain were targeted for data collection. Corporate executives, purchase managers, operations managers, and store managers were especially filtered out for data collection, as these directly deal with tier one suppliers in the automobile and electronics industries. A non-probability convenience sampling strategy was used. A questionnaire was developed on the basis of scales used in the study of Doney and Cannon (1997) for “trust in supply chain”, for “supplier network responsiveness” and “competitive advantage”, scales of A.A Thatte (2007) were used, for “firm performance” scales of Akgun et al (2007) were used. The questionnaire was based on a “five-point Likert scale” ranging from “strongly agree (SA) to strongly disagree (SD)”. Questionnaires were distributed to supply chain managers both online and offline. A total of 356 questionnaires were distributed, of which 180 were returned duly filled in, for a response rate of 51%. Of the 180 filled questionnaires, 21 were not usable as they were incomplete. A total of 159 questionnaires (45% of the total distributed questionnaires) were used for the analysis.

3.3 Independent Variables

Trust in the supply chain was taken as the independent variable in the present study. Trust was measured using the scales used by Doney and Cannon (1997). nine (9) items were included in the instrument, which were measured on a “five-point Likert scale” ranging from “strongly agree (SA) to strongly disagree (SD)”.

3.4 Dependent Variables

The dependent variables of the present study were Supplier Network Responsiveness (SNR), Competitive Advantage (CA), and Firm Performance (FP). For measuring Supplier Network Responsiveness, scales of A. A. Thatte (2007) were used consisting of seven (7) items in total. For Competitive Advantage also, scales used in the study of A. A. Thatte (2007) were used consisting of eight (8) items in total. For Firm Performance, scales used in the study of Akgun et. al. (2007) was used consisting of seven (7) items in total. All variables were measured on a “five-point Likert scale” ranging from “strongly agree (SA) to strongly disagree (SD)”.

4. Data Analysis and Results

Data analysis was conducted in two phases.

Phase 1 involved the scale development stage. In this phase, Exploratory Factor Analysis was performed using SPSS 23. In the EFA, Bartlett’s test of sphericity was conducted to check the overall significance of the correlation among the variables. “Kaiser-Mayer-Olkin” measure of sampling adequacy was tested which came to 0.936 (>0.6). This signifies that the correlation between the variables was highly significant.

The total variance explained (TVE) value was 35.99% (>45%). Table 1 (Annexure) shows the factor loadings of the individual items of all variables. Table 2 (Annexure) shows the “KMO and Bartlett test of sphericity”.

After conducting the sample adequacy test, the next step in the scale development phase was to run a reliability analysis. A reliability test was conducted to check the consistency of the data in terms of what it intended to measure. The overall value of Cronbach’s alpha was 0.973 which was greater than 0.6. The dimension-wise value of Cronbach’s alpha (α) is shown in Table 3 (Annexure).

After completing the Exploratory Factor Analysis and reliability tests, the next step in the scale development phase was to conduct Confirmatory Factor Analysis using Amos 23. Table 3 (Annexure) represents the values of “CMIN/DF”, “Goodness of Fit (GFI)”, “Adjusted Goodness of Fit (AGFI)”, “CFI”, and “RMSEA”. The result of Confirmatory Factor Analysis shows that the model is perfectly fit for the study.

Phase 2 of the analysis was the hypothesis testing stage. The hypotheses were tested using Structural Equation Modelling. The estimated value and P value of all the relationships are given in Table 5 (Annexure).

The relationship between trust and supplier network responsiveness was positive, as the estimate value for this relationship is 0.926. This means that trust has a positive impact on “supplier network responsiveness”. The “P value” for this relationship was less than 0.05 which means that the independent variable “trust” has a significant impact on the dependent variable “supplier network responsiveness”. Therefore, hypothesis 1 i.e. higher level of trust in supply chain has a significant impact on supplier network responsiveness, is accepted.

The relationship between “supplier network responsiveness” and “competitive advantage” was also positive, as the estimate value for this relationship is 0.227. This means that “supplier network responsiveness” has a positive impact on “competitive advantage”. The “P value” for this relationship was less than 0.05 which means the independent variable “supplier network responsiveness” has a significant impact on the dependent variable “competitive advantage”. Therefore, hypothesis 2 i.e. higher level of supplier network responsiveness has a significant impact on competitive advantage, is accepted.

The relationship between “supplier network responsiveness” and “competitive advantage” was also positive, as the estimate value for this relationship is 0.497. This means that “competitive advantage” has a positive impact on “firm performance”. The P value for this relationship was less than 0.05 which means the independent variable “competitive advantage” has a significant impact on the dependent variable “firm performance”. Therefore, Hypothesis 3, that is, competitive advantage has a significant impact on firm performance, is accepted.

5. Discussion

1. Hypothesis 1 (H1) was found to be true; that is, **a higher level of “trust” in the supply chain has a significant impact on “supplier network responsiveness”**. The results show that a higher level of “trust in supply chain” has a positive relationship with the level of “supplier network responsiveness”. Firms that maintain a level of trust with their suppliers have a responsive and efficient supply chain.

2. Hypothesis 2 (H2) was also found to be true; that is, **a higher level of “supplier network responsiveness” has a significant impact on “competitive advantage”**. The results of the analysis show that there is a positive relationship between “supplier network responsiveness” and “competitive advantage”. This means if suppliers learn to react effectively and efficiently, the manufacturer (supplier’s buyer) will be benefitted by getting “competitive advantage” in terms of “price”, “quality”, and “delivery”.

3. Hypothesis 3 (H3) was found to be true; that is, **“competitive advantage” has a significant impact on firm performance**. The results show that “competitive advantage” affects “firm performance” positively. This means that if a firm obtains an advantage over its competitors, it will perform better.

4. Conclusion

This study was conducted to determine the role of trust in a manufacturer-supplier relationship and whether the presence of “trust in the supply chain” affects “supply chain responsiveness”, “competitive advantage,” and “firm performance”. From the above discussion, we can conclude the following points:

1. Firms that maintain a level of trust with their suppliers have a responsive and efficient supply chain.
2. Firms that maintain good relationships with their suppliers tend to obtain more benefits as compared to their competitors.
3. If suppliers learn to react effectively and efficiently, the manufacturer (supplier’s buyer) will benefit by getting “competitive advantage” in terms of “price”, “quality”, and “delivery”.
4. Firms with “competitive advantage” (in any form) perform better than their competitors.
5. Firms with responsive supply chains have a better ability to introduce new products in the market and deliver on time.

5. Expected Contribution

- The present study provides a deep and thorough understanding of the importance of trust in the supply chain field.
- The present study provides a proposed framework by compiling more than two frameworks used in earlier studies.
- The present study provides a complete view of the relationship between a manufacturer and its supplier. According to this research, a positive and trustworthy relationship between a manufacturer and its supplier is very beneficial.

- This study shows how a higher level of trust is related to “supply chain responsiveness”, “competitive advantage”, and “firm performance”.
- The present study opens doors for an empirical investigation using this proposed framework and hypotheses to conduct research for industries other than the automobile and electronics.

Conflicts of Interest

The authors declare that they have no conflicts of interest.

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Annexure

Table 1: Exploratory Factor Analysis (item wise)

Item code	Items	Factor loadings
TR1	When it comes to things that are important to our company, our company can depend on the supplier’s support.	0.554
TR2	Our company’s key supplier is trustworthy.	0.867
TR3	Our company’s key supplier fully trusts our production ability.	0.857
TR4	Our company’s key supplier keeps promises it makes to our firm.	0.796
TR5	Our company’s key supplier is always honest with us.	0.785
TR6	Our company believes the information that our key supplier provides us.	0.811
TR7	Our company’s key supplier is genuinely concerned that our business succeeds.	0.819
TR8	When making important decisions, our company’s key supplier considers our welfare as well as its own.	0.875
TR9	Our company trusts our key supplier keeps our best interests in mind.	0.869
SNR1	Our company’s key supplier changes product volume in a relatively short time.	0.647
SNR2	Our company’s key supplier changes product mix in a relatively short time.	0.425

SNR3	Our company's key supplier consistently accommodates our requests.	0.680
SNR4	Our company's key supplier provides quick inbound logistics to us.	0.889
SNR5	Our company's key supplier has outstanding on-time delivery record with us.	0.908
SNR6	Our company's key supplier easily changes its capacity in order to address our company's changing needs.	0.227
SNR7	Our company's key supplier effectively expedites our company's emergency orders.	0.553
CA1	Our company is able to offer prices as low or lower than our competitors	0.422
CA2	Our company offers products that are highly reliable	0.313
CA3	Our company offers products that are very durable	0.081
CA4	Our company offers high quality products to our customers	0.134
CA5	Our company delivers customer orders on time	0.102
CA6	Our company provides customized products	0.068
CA7	Our company is first in the market in introducing new products.	0.089
CA8	Our company has time-to-market lower than industry average.	0.200
FP1	In comparison to the competitors, our company has more return on investment (ROI)	0.382
FP2	In comparison to the competitors, our company has more market share	0.530
FP3	In comparison to the competitors, our company has more sales	0.590
FP4	In comparison to the competitors, our company has more profitability.	0.535
FP5	In comparison to the competitors, our company has more earnings.	0.548
FP6	In comparison to the competitors, our company has more gross margins (profitability/total sales).	0.632
FP7	In comparison to the competitors, our company has more market value.	0.323

Table 2: KMO and Bartlett Test of Sphericity

Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy.		.936
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity	Approx. Chi-Square	11841.348
	Df	465
	Sig.	.000

Table 3: Reliability Analysis

S no	Dimension	(α)	N
1.	TR	0.983	9
2.	SNR	0.910	7
3.	CA	0.878	8
4.	FP	0.960	7

Where, TR stands for the mean of all the items of Trust

SNR stands for mean of all the items of Supplier Network Responsiveness

CA stands for mean of all the items of Competitive Advantage

FP stands for mean of all the items of Firm Performance

Table 4: Confirmatory Factor Analysis

Fit Indices	Observed Value	Recommended Value
CMIN/DF	3.19	<3.5
GFI	.833	>0.8
AGFI	.847	>0.8
CFI	.907	>0.8
RMSEA	.089	<0.1

Table 5: Structural Equation Modelling (Estimates and P value)

S.No.	Independent Variable	Dependent Variable	Estimates	P value	Result
1.	TR	SNR	0.926	<0.05	Significant
2.	SNR	CA	0.227	<0.05	Significant
3.	CA	FP	0.497	<0.05	Significant